

LINGUISTIC GAME IN THE SYSTEM OF MEANS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of linguistic games in the lessons of Russian as a foreign language, proposes a classification of linguistic games with examples.*

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Scientific and technological progress, a rapid flow of information, the ability to communicate in social networks with representatives of other countries provides for the study of languages, including Russian. Today the requirement of the time is a creative approach to all activities, activity and independence of all members of society. The formation of such qualities should take place at school. Consequently, it is during this period that the most important task is to awaken students' interest in cognitive activity, in particular, in the study of the Russian language.

However, reliance on grammar, as well as on any linguistic aspect of speech activity, takes on various forms and content, depending on the characteristics of the material used, its complexity, and its relationship with its analogue in the native language. The teacher's maturity, his ability to make the right choice of teaching method in the presence of different trends in the approach to the pedagogical process in a foreign language is especially clearly manifested in cases where the problems are related precisely to the peculiarities of the language material. After all, it is in it that the specificity of our subject is manifested, its difference from the native language. Many works have been written about teaching methods, methodological recommendations that cover various aspects of this issue, but nevertheless, one can single out their commonality in that all methodological concepts have a single goal - to maximize the learning process [7].

To instill interest in learning, to form an internal need for continuous replenishment of knowledge is the main task of the teacher. The fact that interest in the case helps to master it, facilitates the work. The personality of a teacher who is passionate about his work is the most important condition for the student's interest in the subject.

The game form of lessons is created by game motivation, which acts as a means of inducing, stimulating children to learning activities.

The implementation of game techniques and situations in the classroom takes place in the following main areas:

the didactic goal is set for children in the form of a game task;

educational activity is subject to the rules of the game;

educational material is used as its means;

an element of competition is introduced into the educational activity, which translates the didactic task into a game one;

successful completion of a didactic task is associated with a game result [9].

In modern conditions, it is also necessary to use various forms and methods of teaching in Russian language lessons. In particular, the use of gaming technologies and linguistic games.

A linguistic game is a language game associated with learning a language and enriching speech, with the development of logical thinking, communicative features of speech in terms of taking into account lexical, grammatical, orthoepic, syntactic features of speech [10].

Various linguistic games in teaching Russian as a foreign language are a means of intensive learning in Russian language lessons, since during the game the information received is processed creatively. Thanks to linguistic games, a favorable communicative and cognitive atmosphere is created, both for children of primary school age and older ones. But you need to take into account the degree of complexity when choosing linguistic games for age categories. Subject to the correct choice of games, the goals and objectives of the educational process, in particular the lesson of the Russian language, are realized. In the course of a linguistic game, students replenish their vocabulary, develop clarity and correctness of speech, create prerequisites for the development of spelling skills, increase activity, worldview potential, and in general, cognitive activity is activated.

Today, there are many classifications of linguistic games: according to the thematic principle, according to the type of lesson, according to the composition of the participants, etc. Based on the basic laws of the subject area, games are divided into:

- Orthoepic - aimed at developing pronunciation skills;
- Lexical - enrich the vocabulary of students, improve speech;
- Grammar - help to consolidate the knowledge gained in sections of grammar in practice, develop spelling skills.

Linguistic games can be used at any stage of the lesson, depending on the goals and objectives. The inclusion of linguistic games in the educational process contributes to the productive assimilation of educational material by students.

Let's consider a few examples of linguistic games

Orthoepic games

For younger students in the foreign language, whose vocabulary is still small, you can offer tasks related to the pronunciation of letters, composing simple words from letters, for example:

- **“Phonetic tongue twister”**:

Ра, ра, ра, ра – начинается игра,
Ры, ры, ры, ры – а у нас в руках шары,
Ре, ре, ре, ре - стоит домик на горе,
Ру, ру, ру, ру – продолжаем мы игру [11]

- **“The letters crumbled”**: making words out of letters – к, о, ш, к, а; д, е, д, у, ш, к, а и т.п.

For older students, phonetic tasks can be offered, such as:

- How to change the word *мел* to shallow place, *угол* – to charcoal, *шест* – to a number, *мол* – to an insect, and *полку* – to a fun dance? (answer: мел – мель, угол – уголь, шест – шесть, мол – моль, полка - полька)
- Which letters need to be replaced in order to change *точка* to *дочка*, *уточка* - to *удочка*, *прутик* – to *прудик*?

Lexical games.

• In a foreign language environment, compared to native speakers, the situation is more complicated, especially when it comes to vocabulary. In this case, age characteristics are not always taken into account. Depending on the lexicon, the following tasks can be offered:

• «**Thematic dictionary**»: compiling a vocabulary on topics - "Vegetables", "Fruits", "Pets", "Wild Animals", etc. with translation into native language.

• «**Printery**»: make words out of words as many as possible: *активизация* – акт, актив, кит, виза, заяц, ваза, як, таз, and other.

Grammar games

The grammar of the Russian language is quite difficult for foreign language students, including Uzbek ones. The grammatical structure of the Uzbek language largely corresponds to the grammar of the Russian language, but also has significant differences. This is especially true for gender, prepositional-case forms, etc.

Grammar games help without loading theoretical material, it is easier to master the rules and apply them in practice.

Examples of grammar games:

• For masculine words, match the feminine pair: ученик – ученица, учитель – учительница, повар – повариха, портной – портниха и т.п.

• Name baby animals: осёл – ослёнок, козёл – козлёнок, тигр – тигрёнок, лиса – лисёнок и др.

• Continue word formation: *лес, лесной, лесник, ... ; гора, горный, пригорок ...*

• Form the plural: *город – города, мост - моста, брат – братья, человек – люди* and so on.

Each teacher, based on the amount of grammatical material, can increase the number of games in the Russian language lessons. A properly selected game helps to develop mental activity, replenish the active vocabulary, instill interest in learning the Russian language in a foreign language.

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